

MODERN APPROACHES IN EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT AND INTEGRATION OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *Nowadays, the interest of both teachers and students in using various methods, innovative technologies, and games to explain the subject in the educational process is increasing day by day. These ways of teaching have replaced the old methods with their greater effectiveness and usefulness. Such innovative technical methods and exercises create opportunities for young people to independently study, analyze, and even draw conclusions on their own. Also, Teaching is a crucial aspect of educational planning and management, with a focus on promoting student self-determination and practical, experimental learning. This study explores various teaching methods in higher education and emphasizes the importance of effective teaching strategies. Qualitative research methods were used to analyze data and the results highlight the need for potential teaching strategies. The study concludes with a discussion and recommendations for improving teaching activities in higher education.*

Keywords: *quality of education, creativity, international standards school management, digital management, modern approaches, educational management, methodologies, technological ways, language barrier, gamification.*

Introduction

In the era of globalization and digital transformation, the issue of increasing the efficiency and quality of the education system is becoming increasingly relevant. In school education, not only is teaching subjects an important task, but also the formation of independent thinking, creativity, and communicative competencies in students. In this regard, the process of teaching English is of particular importance, since it is the main tool for integrating into the global community.

In the management system, modern educational management approaches, digital management, innovative methodologies, and assessment systems based on international standards determine the development of an educational institution. This article discusses modern approaches in educational management and the integration of innovative technologies in English language teaching.

1. Modern approaches to educational management

In modern educational institutions, management should focus not only on organizational management, but also on quality monitoring, supporting teachers, and creating an environment that meets the needs of students. In this sense, the following areas are relevant:

Digital management systems. Electronic diaries, online rating systems, and analysis through big data increase management efficiency. International standards for quality assessment. Assessment based on indicators such as PISA, TIMSS, and CEFR aligns the educational process with international criteria.

Innovative leadership. The school head uses modern management models (transformational and interactive leadership) when making strategic decisions.

2. Innovative technologies in English teaching

The introduction of foreign languages into our lives not only benefits teachers and students alike but also encourages them to work harder. We know that mastering the language of a particular people, getting used to it, its rules, and overcoming its “language barrier” takes a lot of time. But this cannot be an obstacle to young people’s education. Today, the techniques and methods of language learning are completely outdated. It is no exaggeration to say that technology has brought about an improvement in both education and our social life. Many methodological methods are being developed to further increase the interest of the younger generation in learning languages. The most common of them today is the gamification method.

According to research results, this method has significantly increased the speed of language learning among young people. You can see games adapted to each area of language. For example, some games are aimed at developing vocabulary, while others are aimed at developing reading comprehension skills. Using games during lessons helps to focus students’ attention on one point. It is especially effective to conduct lessons in the form of a game with elementary school students. We know that elementary school students are cheerful and curious. Simply teaching and memorizing rules may seem boring to them.

In addition, using not only a blackboard and marker, but also colored pencils, pictures related to various lesson topics, short silent films and animations on an electronic screen also has a positive effect on students' attitude to the lesson. For example, the proven method - Tabbo words (Forbidden words) - this interesting game helps students use synonymous words and their definitions. The use of synonyms ensures fluency of speech, beautiful speech. In particular, in English, one should not make mistakes related to the use of words, because many words in English that mean the same thing are used according to the context of the sentence. This game helps to be careful in this regard. In this, groups are formed, that is, students sit opposite each other. Each team chooses one person from their team to sit on the chair opposite them. The teacher goes behind the students and holds up a word written on a large piece of paper. The students sitting on the chair should not be able to see this word. The member of the team sitting on the chair is given some time to say the word that the teacher is holding up.

20 objects. This game allows you to test students' memory and vocabulary at the same time. All you need is a blackboard and 20 objects that are in the classroom. All the objects are laid out on the table. And all the students are called and asked to look at the objects. Then the objects are covered so that they are not visible. Students must return to their places and write the name of the object they remembered on paper. Then the name of the remaining objects is written on the blackboard. And the students check what they have written themselves. In this process, they remember their mistakes well when correcting the misspelled words.

The next game is called “Character”. This game is more suitable for high school students. Because when the student reads the given text, he is required to fully understand it and have high vocabulary skills. Students are given a sheet of paper with a text. Words are omitted in the text, and students must find these words based on the content of the sentence. However, this game can also be used for elementary school students; that is, instead of dots, pictures or stickers are placed that indicate the hidden word.

The most common method among teachers is the “Brainstorming” method. Dilafruz Khidoyatova says that she uses this method 7-8 times in one lesson. This is the most effective

technique for attracting and engaging students in the lesson, a technique that can kill ten birds with one stone. Dilafruz Khidoyatova: “I always try this method before starting a lesson. I write the topic on the board and ask the students what they know about it. At first, two or three students answer. Even if the ideas are wrong, I don’t keep quiet. Then the other students’ attention to the lesson increases spontaneously, they try to say something even if they guess.”

“Fishing” game. A picture of the sea is drawn on one side of the board, and a picture of an aquarium on the other. There are fish in the sea. The student catches one of the fish in the sea and answers the questions on the back. If the answer is correct, the fish is put in the aquarium, and if it is incorrect, the fish is released into the sea. “Rocket” game. A picture of a rocket is shown on the electronic board and there is a bag of questions in it. It must be free of cargo to fly to another planet. Students are divided into three groups, and whichever group answers the questions correctly and quickly, the rocket will fly. As a gift to the students, the information from the planet to which the rocket flew will be revealed as the topic of today's lesson.

Along with organizing games during the lesson, the use of techniques based on new methods and innovative ideas is also a requirement of today's developing era. For example, teaching students to work with technologies and introducing them to their good sides is the duty of every student. In particular, ChatGPT, if used for the purpose of gaining knowledge, is a source of much unique information. The Kahoot website is also a very useful electronic system for reinforcing the topic. The student can enter here at any time, complete the tests given, and work on their mistakes. In addition to traditional methods, new pedagogical approaches in the process of teaching English increase student motivation and ensure effectiveness. Artificial intelligence-based platforms. Chatbots, online translators, and adaptive programs provide an individual approach.

Gamification. Combining tests and tasks with game elements encourages students to actively participate.

Online resources and mobile applications. Tools such as Duolingo, Quizlet, Kahoot enhance independent learning.

Multimedia technologies. The use of audio-video materials develops students' listening comprehension and communication skills.

3. Integration process

The combination of modern technologies in educational management and English teaching leads to a number of effective results:

School management can evaluate English lessons through digital monitoring and create individual learning plans. When the teacher uses methods based on international standards in the lesson process, students are well prepared for international exams (IELTS, TOEFL). As a result of integration, students not only learn the language but also develop digital literacy and critical thinking competencies.

Conclusion

In today's developing world, delivering lessons using too simple and old-fashioned methods can lead to a decline in students' interest in education. Therefore, when organizing a lesson, each student should use games related to the lesson, methods that motivate and support the student. This approach helps to arouse the interest of young people and increase the level of logical thinking. International experience shows that the combination of modern technologies in educational management and English language teaching not only increases the quality of education but also strengthens the reputation of the academic institution in the international arena. This

approach serves to bring students' knowledge closer to global standards, improve the skills of teachers, and create an innovative environment in the educational institutions.

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